

650 nm LED Integrated in PON Optical Sub-Assembly for Future PON Management

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Abstract: A 50 MBit/s link based on a 650 nm LED emitter integrated in a PON optical subassembly is proposed. Transmission through up to 5 km of single mode fiber is demonstrated. Use cases like PON troubleshooting or PtP management are discussed. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The completion of the 50G-PON standard by the ITU-T [1] has moved the research effort on the next generation Passive Optical Network (PON), namely the Very High Speed PON (VHSP). This next generation can be based on high speed (≥ 100 Gbit/s) Intensity Modulation and Direct Detection (IM/DD) [2] or coherent technology [3, 4]. What is certain is that optical access will have to support the coexistence of several PON generations on the same fiber infrastructure [5] and a combination of several ONUs (multi-vendors fiber gateway) which increase operational complexity. The need to facilitate event management and telemetry is a growing trend toward autonomous network. Presently, auxiliary channel is not used due to the extra cost of the implementation of an additional transmission channel. Nevertheless, optical gateway could implement a common and low cost red Light Emitting Diode (LED) to achieve a function of automatic Visual Fault Locators (VFL). This LED will help field technicians to identify and localize fiber defaults to reduce the overall time to repairment. One can also imagine the utilization of this LED to transmit Operations, Administration and Maintenance (OAM) informations such as diagnosis and ONU identification data to a technician. This can facilitate the connection of new ONUs and troubleshooting. Beside having only a red signal showing visually to the technician operating at the splitter if the ONU is properly connected, this red signal could also carry useful information such as the ONU ID or error codes IDs with a proper device able to receive and decode it. Transmission at 650 nm till the OLT which may be 20 km away from users seems difficult due to high losses of red light in Standard Single Mode Fiber (SSMF). However, there is an opportunity to use a LED to transmit information from the ONU to the street cabinet as described in figure 1. Indeed, the mean distance between the ONU and the street cabinet is about 4 km on Orange network in France [6]. Several technologies like Dedicated Activation Wavelength [7] or pilot-tones [8] were proposed to create an auxiliary channel for the management in optical access networks. Some telemetry information can be sent this way. Another usage is a low-bitrate data transmission channel. However, low speed transmission need to be realised between ONU and OLT. Typically, when traffic demand is low, the high speed link can be shut down and communication switches to the low-speed auxiliary channel. This will allow energy consumption reduction. Point to Point (PtP) link could also be of interest for co-transmission of visible light for the same purposes. Obviously, there is no optical coupler which can be problematic to cross for visible light [9]. But this kind of auxiliary channel can also be implemented on particular PON architecture such as short reach PON for intra-enterprise, intra-campus or Fiber To The Room (FTTR) applications (with a mechanism to multiplex different ONUs: TDM, FDM, ...). The utilization of such an auxiliary link for ONU ranging can also dramatically decrease the PON jitter value in bypassing the quiet window. Mean jitter is usually quite important in PON system due to quiet ranging window when the OLT imposes to all ONUs to stop transmitting to allow new ONUs to range in the PON. Jitter reduction can then help to meet the requirement for Time Sensitive Network (TSN) application for future such as mobile x-haul and industry 4.0 [10, 11].

In this paper, we propose to use a 650 nm LED emitter to transmit low speed data for PON management and troubleshooting like described in figure 1, in addition to its original visual fault location purpose. We use a 650 nm LED integrated in an optical sub-assembly with Gigabit capable PON (G-PON) ONU emitter and receiver. The LED was modulated at 50 Mbit/s using IM/DD. A first part is dedicated to the study of the curvature loss on 650 nm signal in SSMF. We assess the reachable fiber range measuring the Bit Error Rate (BER) and the coexistence with a triple G/XGS/50G-PON commercial system.

The experimental setup used in this work is presented on figure 1 (b). The LED is modulated with a Pulse Pattern Generator (PPG) in NRZ-OOK with a PRBS of length $2^{15} - 1$ at 50 Mbit/s. The amplitude of the modulated signal is set to 1 V peak-to-peak and the bias is equal to 1.5 V. The optical spectrum of the LED when biased at 2.2 V without modulation (static) is shown in figure 2 (c). The emission is centered at 653.8 nm (visible red). A G-PON emitter and a G-PON receiver are co-packaged in a triple Optical Sub-Assembly ("triOSA"). These G-PON Tx/Rx are not used to transmit data in this work. At the output of the triOSA, the signal propagates through 0 to 5 km of SSMF before reaching a 155 MHz 3 dB Electro-Optical bandwidth (EO-BW) PIN photodiode. The

Fig. 1. Schematic of the 650 nm troubleshooting link (a). Experimental setup for transmission performances assesment.

optical signal is coupled with the photodiode using a micro-lensed fiber. The electrical signal is then sent to an Error Detector (ED) computing the BER in real time. The electrical signal is also sent to a Digital Communication Analyzer oscilloscope (DCA) with a 30 GHz electrical bandwidth allowing eye diagram visualization.

2. Characterization and transmission performances

The mean optical power characterization measured at the triOSA fiber output as function of the voltage applied to the LED is presented in figure 2 (b). The inset is a photograph of the triOSA module. A saturation of the emitted power happens when voltage is above 2.15 V. At this voltage, the LED consumes 14 mA. At 650 nm, the single mode fiber is highly multimode and presents poor guiding capacity. An issue can arise from the bending loss of the 650 nm signal in SSMF. A characterization of the loss induced by fiber bending is presented in figure 2 (a). Loss increasing can be observed for bending radius from 250 mm to 100 mm. After this point, the losses decreases before increasing again. This behavior is due to the cladding mode excitation when the fiber bending is increased. At a certain value, the power is re-injected into the core and the loss decreases before increasing again when the bending radius is very low. In our experiment, we have used fiber coils with 34 to 52.5 mm bending radius. The electrical eye diagram at the output of the photodiode are presented in figure 3 (a) for different fiber reach. The eye diagrams are measured with the parameters described in the experimental setup section. In these conditions, the emitter's Extinction Ratio (ER) at 50 Mbit/s is equal to 9.2 dB. An opened eye can be observed in back to back and after up to 5 km. After 4 km, the peak-to-peak voltage at photodiode output is too low for the ED used in this work. The mean received optical power is measured with a silicon sensor at the output of the micro-lensed fiber used to coupled the light on the photodiode. The transmission does not suffer from severe Inter-Symbol Interference (ISI) as suggested by the sharp transition between symbols 1 and 0. We can observe the influence of modal dispersion for fiber reach of 0 and 5 km through the transition degradation. The main limitation of a visible light transmission on a deployed telecommunication network is then the attenuation. The poor guiding capacity of the SSMF commonly used in access network limits the performance.

Real time 50 Mbit/s BER measurements are reported in figure 3 (b) as a function of SSMF length. An error free ($BER < 1.10^{-8}$) transmission is obtained at up to 4200 m fiber reach. For 4200 m and longer fiber, we add an electrical amplifier at the output of the photodiode. This electrical amplifier exhibit a 1 GHz electrical bandwidth and 23.4 dB gain at +12.3 V driving voltage. We now assess the coexistence of the 650 nm auxiliary channel described in this work with a G/XGS/50G-PON system on the same fiber. The experimental setup described in Fig.3 (c) is used. The coexistence is realized thanks to two optical couplers to mix the signals coming from the three ONUs with the signal from the 650 nm LED and on the other side, the signal coming from the triple PON Module at OLT. The optical spectrum captured in the downstream direction shows the G-PON, XGS-PON, 50G-PON and 650 nm wavelength coexisting (Fig. 3 (d)). At up to 3 km fiber propagation, the 650 nm transmission remains error free and no packet error can be observed on the PON system with Ethernet traffic configured at each PON maximum capacity. The fiber reach of the 650 nm is limited to 3 km due to additional losses coming from the couplers that could be replaced by visible-infrared diplexers.

Fig. 2. Bending loss/lap in function of the bending radius at 650 nm in SSMF (a). Mean fiber output optical power in function of the voltage applied to the 650 nm LED (b). LED optical spectrum (c).

Fig. 3. Electrical eye diagram at the output of the photodiode in back-to-back and after 5000 m (a). BER in function of the fiber length (b). Simplified experimental setup for coexistence with tri-combo PON system (c). Optical spectrum in downstream direction (d).

3. Conclusion

We have explored the possible utilization of a 650 nm LED emitter originally integrated for visual fault detection to create an auxiliary channel working at up to 50 Mbit/s. An error free transmission over 4.3 km reach on SSMF is demonstrated in real time using an integrated 650 nm LED made for visual fault detection. The error free loss budget is equal to 25 dB at 650 nm. The reach was limited in our experiments due to several factor. First, the launch power coupled into the fiber at the output of the LED is limited to -0.1 dBm. Eye security limit at 650 nm is 5.8 dBm (1M laser class in MMF) [12]. Then, the emitted power can be increased by nearly 6 dB bringing the loss budget to 31 dB at 650 nm. The second limiting factor in our experiment is the mismatch between the emitter modulation speed and the receiver EO-BW as well as a difficult coupling between the end of the fiber and the photodiode. An increased loss budget would allow the use of such 650 nm link for management of optical access link (Short reach PON and PtP). This can also permit the implementation of deep sleep mode of high speed links. As discussed in the introduction, a low speed and low cost visible IM/DD link can also be used to replace the high speed IR link when traffic usages are low.

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